

Introduction:

I would like to thank you once again for being willing to participate in the interview aspect of our study. As I have mentioned to you before, the study seeks to understand how professional historians assess the value of generative AI and what pedagogical strategies they may currently be implementing, or plan to implement in the future, that include AI tools. The aim of this research is to document the possible problems and benefits of generative AI in the field of history and the humanities more broadly and analyze their implications. Our interview today will last approximately 30-45 minutes. In that time, I will ask a series of questions about the topic of AI in education. The interview will be audio-recorded for analysis purposes. The recording will be accessible to the research team only.

Question 1:

What sort of technology tools do you use in your everyday life? For example, do you use voice assistants such as Alexa or Google Home? Do you use Turnitin for grading purposes?

Question 1a:

Do you feel comfortable with these tools and their presence in your life? Why/Why not?

Question 2:

Do you use generative AI in teaching? If not, will you do so in the future?

(IF NO) Question 2b:

Why do you not use generative AI?

- How do you think of using generative AI for history teaching, compared to using it to teach other fields or disciplines?
- Does your institution have any guidelines for using generative AI in teaching? Does the guideline impact your decision?
- What are your views regarding the use of generative AI and plagiarism?

Question 2c:

If you plan to use it in the future, what motivates you?

(IF YES, Move to Question 3)

Question 3.1:

Why did you decide to use generative AI for teaching activities either in the classroom or for administrative functions such as grading?

Question 3.1 (a):

- What do you think are the benefits and value of using generative AI for teaching?

Question 3.1 (b):

- What concerns or hesitations do you have regarding the use of generative AI in teaching, if any?

Question 3.2

How do you use generative AI for classroom activities and/or administrative functions?

Question 3.2 (a):

- What are the main tasks for which you use generative AI? What generative AI tools do you use in teaching?

Question 3.2 (b):

- Is generative AI an effective tool for students, such as its use as a “research assistant”?

Question 3.2 (c):

- Have you had any challenges with implementing generative AI in your teaching? What do you think are the causes of that challenge, and how might it be overcome?

Question 3.2 (d):

- What other teaching or educational applications of generative AI do you think may exist for the field of history? What generative AI tools do you wish to have to teach history, if any?